

Banda Aceh City - Building Damage Information System (BDIS) After Sumatera (Indonesia) Earthquake 2004

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Abstract- GIS based Building damage information system (BDIS) has been developed using a combination of GIS Data, high resolution IKONOS images, aerial photographs and substantiated through field surveys as well as the data collected from various institutions.

The present building earthquake resistance (PER), was calculated using formula $BER - NER = PER$ where building earthquake resistance-BER (in richter scale) and number of earthquake resistance-NER (in richter scale). Building earthquake resistance (BER) and present building earthquake resistance (PER) are calculated (in richter scale) using constant value of resistance equal with 0.1 (CR=0.1). All result are stored and managed in a geo-database structured as relational database management system (RDBMS).

In pilot area in Setui village (Affected by Earthquake not by tsunami), type of building usage predominated by non commercial building with more than 90 percent with buildings age between 3 to 40 years. Most of the buildings with commercial functions are older than 30 years with building size generally wider than others part automatically have level of low earthquake resistance (less than 5 richter scale).

Keywords : Building Damage, Information System, Banda Aceh, Earthquake, GIS

I. INTRODUCTION

A big earthquake triggered Sumatra Island on December 26th, 2004, registering a magnitude 9.0 on the Richter scale [5], it was followed by a big tsunami known as Indian Ocean Tsunami (IOT) which caused death of over 270,000 people in 11 countries across Asia and Africa. In Asia, the fatalities mostly happened in Indonesia, Sri Lanka, India and Maldives [2]

The worst affected areas were Banda Aceh City (BAC), the capital city of the Aceh Province, many buildings and infrastructure were collapsed or failed, especially transportation and communication facility [3]. Released estimation that about 19 percent of the approximately 820,000 building units (about 151,600 units) in the affected districts suffered an average of about 50 percent

damage while about 14 percent or around 127,300 building completely destroyed [3]. Specially in BAC, estimated total 27,796 building units, 35 percent are classified as totally destruction, 29 percent on slightly till moderate damage condition and 36 percent just flooded upon tsunami [4].

Spatially, building damage in BAC showing specific pattern in where for all damage level is forms continual pattern with the relatively same direction from south-west to north-east and parallel with coastline. Totally destruction area is the widest area generally located at the 1.6 km from coastline with average distance for all damage level is around 2.2 km [4]

After occurrence of disaster, devastated area in the city will be changed enormously, availability of building damage information system (BDIS) is very important for fast damage and loss calculation after the event. Boundary of individual building can be extracted from the help of high resolution imagery and aerial photograph and various attribute data can be developed in one system in the geographical information system database (geo-database).

Usage of remote sensing dan GIS for disaster management have been studied many times and applied in various parts of the world. This has been shown by many reports and researches regarding this particular study. Recent researches in damage detection have employed remote sensing for quick building damage detection and quick damage assessment [6].

These studies are focusing in developing building damage information system (BDIS) using high resolution imagery, aerial photograph and GIS data.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Study Area

Using available village survey data collected in January 2005 for limited location in Setui Village, building damage information system developed in more detail.

Setui village is a part of Baiturrahman sub district located in southwest of BAC. FIGURE 1 is showing location of Setui village

Fig. 1. Location of Setui village in Banda Aceh City

B. Data Availability and Sources

Building data available and applied in this information system consist of building map, level of building damage, data of building usage, data of building size, number of rooms, number of floor, number of people in each buildings, age of building and present building resistance. Building map with individual attribute such as level of damage and building usage especially in Setui village are obtained by *clip one theme based on another* option in geoprocessing operation between building map and village boundary. Building size in square meter (M2) obtained with automatically calculating using XTool extension in Arcview software based on length and wide of each building. Number of room, number of floors and number of people in each building are available in spreadsheets formats and joined with building object through object ID.

C. Setui Building Damage Database

Integration building as individual objects and attribute in table done with object attribute join using column of the building ID as primary key of each object. Joint object and attribute processed with joint function in Arcview software in *.dbf* database formats.

Setui building damage database created as a object relational database management system (ORDBMS) comprises a set of tables, each a two dimensional list of record containing attribute of damage. Building damage data stored as feature classes in separate theme such as level of damage, building usage, level of inundation, building size, number of floor, number of room and number of people in each building. Object classes are store in standard database table in a two dimensional array of rows and columns. Table rows contain 580 building object and the column contains properties of each object or attributes. Actual coordinate value stored in highly compressed binary form and located as *invisible* file in database.

In database, level of building damage classify based on EMS classification into three classes that is grade 1, grade 2 and grade 3. Building usage classify based on function of each building into five class that is commercial building, non commercial building, mosque, school and hospital. Level of inundation classified into three classes

that is 4 meters, 5 meters and 6 meters. Especially for building size, number of floor, number of room and number of people in each building, data stored as actual value of each attribute object. For analysis purposes, building size classified into 4 classes using natural break classification type that is building size 0 -100 m², 101 – 200 m², 201 – 300 m² and building size more than 300 m². The same classification method applied for number of room and number of people in each building. Number of floor is classified into three classes that is one floor, two floors and three floors. FIGURE 2 is showing database of building damage in Setui village.

Fig. 2. Database of Setui BDIS

D. Building Earthquake Resistance

Using individual age and earthquake resistance information, present individual building resistance for earthquake in Setui can be calculated and describe the spatial distribution. Age of each building calculated with following formula:

$$\text{BCY} - \text{PR} = \text{BE}$$

Age of individual building continues calculated with constant value of resistance (CR = 0.1) with the aim to find number of earthquake resistance using following formula:

$$\text{BE} * \text{CR} = \text{NER}$$

Using value of **NER**, present building earthquake resistance can be calculated with following formula:

$$\text{BER} - \text{NER} = \text{PER}$$

BCY = Year of Building Construction

PR = Present Year

BE = Age of Building

CR = Constant Value of Resistance

NER = Number of Earthquake Resistance (in Richter scale)

BER = Building Earthquake Resistance (in Richter scale)

PER = Present Building Earthquake Resistance (in Richter scale)

Calculation process conducted automatically using ArcView software and with same time updated of the BDIS database.

III. SETUI BUILDING DAMAGE INFORMATION SYSTEM (BDIS)

Using available data, assessment of building damage conducted in Setui village by comparing number of buildings floors, building sizes, number of rooms, building usage and number of people in each damage levels.

Based on EMS classification, damage level in Setui village classified into three classes they are moderate structural damage (G3), slightly damage (G2) and no structural damage (G1)[1]. From 573 units in this village, building with damage level G1 reaching 388 unit or 67.6 percent and following by building with damage level G2 are 159 units and building with damage level G3 are 26 units.

A. Number of Floor and Level of Damage

Building with number of floor is one dominating in this village reaching around 80 percent or 458 unit and generally experience damage at level G1 and G2 reaching total 437 units. Number building unit and the damage of each number of building floor is showing in TABLE I

Buildings with number of floor is one and two, experience damage at level of damage G3 located clusterly in northwest part with not more than twenty building unit. Buildings with number of floor is one, two and three and experience damage in G2 level generally located in northwest and north part, small part located in the southwest at the cross of main road in at the center part of this village. The big part of building with G1 level generally located in south and east part and few number of building clusterly at the cross of the main road in north part. Spatial distribution of each number of buildings and level of damage can be seen in FIGURE 3.

TABLE I
NUMBER OF BUILDING UNIT AND LEVEL OF DAMAGE IN EACH BUILDING FLOOR

No. of Building Floor	G1	G2	G3
1	311	125	22
2	61	18	4
3	10	16	-

B. Building Size and Level of Damage

Building size in Setui village highly varied from less than 10 m2 till 1430 m2. In this assessment, building size classified into four classes are less than 100 m2, 101 – 200 m2, 2001 – 300 m2 and more than 300 m2. Building with size 101 – 200 m2 dominating in this village around 35 percent or 202 units and following by building with size less than 100 m 2 around 195 units and building with size more than 300 m2 reaching 89 units and building size 201 – 300 m2 with 87 units. See TABLE III for more detail.

Overlay between building damage and building size showing variation of number of building unit and the level of damage in each building size. From that table we can see buildings unit in this village are predominated by building with damage level G1 especially building with size less than 100 m2 and 101 – 200 m2 with the total amount reaching 267 unit. From the total unit which is experience slightly damage (G2), building with size less

than 100 m2 and 101- 200 m2 dominating in this village consist of 50 and 58 unit. Only small part (26 units) from the total of building unit classified as moderate damage and that's building generally have size less than 200 m2. Number of units in each building size and the level of damage can be seen in TABEL II and FIGURE 4.

TABLE II
NUMBER OF BUILDING UNIT AND LEVEL OF DAMAGE IN EACH BUILDING SIZE

Building Size (M2)	G1	G2	G3
> = 100	136	50	9
101 – 200	131	58	13
201 – 300	58	28	1
> 300	63	23	3

Fig. 3. Distribution of Number of Building Floor in Each of Damage Level

Fig. 4. Distribution of Building Size in Each of Damage Level

C. Number of Room and Level of Damage

Number of room in area study predominated by building unit with 2 – 5 rooms with total 501 unit and following by building unit with 6 – 10 rooms, 11 – 15 room and building with more than 20 room. There are not buildings in this area with number of room between 16 and 20 rooms.

Analysis result is showing strong correlation between building size and number of room in each building. Buildings with size relatively bigger tend to have more room inside the building. Such as map of building size, building with number of room more than 6 relatively located near from main road at the center of the village. Overlay between map of number of room and level of building damage resulting information is showing in Table 4.8. Based on level of damage, only small units (26 units) are experience damage till moderate level (G3) and more than 90 percents others experience from non structural damage (G1) and slightly damage (G2). From total building unit in G1 level of damage, more than 88 percents consist of 2 – 5 rooms and only and less than 22 percent have room more than 5.

TABLE III
NUMBER OF ROOM IN EACH BUILDING UNIT AND LEVEL OF DAMAGE

No. Of Room	G1	G2	G3
2 - 5	342	134	25
6 - 10	44	24	1
11 – 15	1	1	-
16 – 20	-	-	-
> 20	1	-	-

Building with number of room more than 5 generally located near from main road in the center of village and only small part located in the north and also south part of this village. Building with damage level G1 (green color) and number of room less than 5 spatially dominating in south part and only small building at the cross of main road in the north. North part of study area predominated by building with level of damage G2 and small number of that level in southwest part (See FIGURE 5). Building with number of room more than 20 (1 unit, red color) and experience moderate damage (G3) is located near from main road in west part of village.

D. Building Usage and Level of Damage

Building usage in this village consist of various type of usage such as commercial, hospital, mosque, non commercial (dwelling) and school. In area study, type of building usage predominated by non commercial building/dwelling with total unit reaching 519 unit or covering more than 90 percent and following by building with type of usage commercial, school, mosque and hospital with number of each 44 unit, 8 unit, 3 unit and 1 unit especially for school. If we calculate number of each building unit based on level of building damage we can see the result in TABEL IV below.

The table is showing building with no structural damage (G1) dominated for all type of usage covering more than 67 percent of the total building unit in the village and those amount 91.7 percent are non commercial building. Only one building is usage for hospital function, experience small/non structural damage (G1) and the others part building with moderately damage (G3) entirely (26 units) is building with type usage of non commercial.

TABLE IV
NUMBER OF BUILDING UNIT BASED ON TYPE OF USAGE
AND LEVEL OF DAMAGE

Type of Building Usage	G1	G2	G3
Commercial	20	22	-
Non Commercial	356	137	26
Hospital	1	-	-
Mosque	3	-	-
School	8	-	-

Spatial analysis result is showing all commercial building generally located at the left and right side of the main road in the center part of the village (pink color). Size of those buildings generally is more than 200 m² and only small number unit less than that size. Commercial building with level of damage G1 spatially located in south part of this area and only small building at the cross of main road in the north. North part of the study area predominated by non commercial building with level of damage G2 and G3 in cluster formation. Small number non commercial building with level of damage G2 located in southwest part of this area and the same case small part of non commercial building with level of damage G1 in north part with cluster forming. Schools basically consist of 8 building unit but actually only is two schools located in south and southwest part of this area. Distribution of each

type of building usage and level of damage can be seen in FIGURE 6.

Fig. 5. Distribution of Number of Room in Each Building and Level of Damage

Fig. 6 Distribution of Building Usage and Level of Damage

IV. BUILDING EARTHQUAKE RESISTANCE

A. Spatial Distribution of Buildings Age

Buildings in Setui village are showing high variation in age between 3 until 40 years of building ages. For analysis needs, age of building in this study are classify into five classes such as age of building less than 15 years, age of building between 15 until 19 years, age of building between 20 until 24 years, age of building between 25 until 29 years and age of building more than 30 years.

Analysis result showing interesting of spatial pattern in which buildings with commercial function and located along of primary street in Setui generally have older than 30 years in age of building (dark green color) and the size of building generally wider than others. From the total building in this village, 59 building units with function as dwelling and have building age more than 30 year are generally located in south part with diffusive spatial patterns. In north part, building with dwelling function are totally 7 units with variation in building size.

Total building with building age less than 15 year consist of 59 units and showing un-regularly in their spatial pattern. Buildings unit with this age located and could be found in south and north part of study area in Setui village.

B. Building Earthquake Resistance

Apply individual data of building age and number of building resistance, individual value of each earthquake building resistance in study area could be calculate and mapped with the aim to shows the spatial pattern of these phenomena. In this study, value of building resistance 5 in Richter scale have been chosen as boundary threshold value and for map visualization, building resistance have been classified into two class such as buildings with resistance value less than 5 in Richter scale and buildings with resistance value more than 5 in Richter scale. Buildings with resistance value more than 5 meaning all building in those class resistance holding up to danger of finite earthquake 5 at scale Richer conversely building with building resistance scale less than 5 at Richter scale meaning that the building to easy to experience damage or

can fall to pieces at occurrences of earthquake with small scale (< 5 Richter Scale).

Fig. 7. Distributions of Class Building Age in Setui Village

Fig. 7 Distributions of Class Building Earthquake Resistance

Building resistance map to danger of earthquake in Setui village showing pattern disseminating where building with high resistance value (>5 Richter scale) and also building with level of low resistance value (<5 Richter scale) spread over either in north and also south in area study (See Figure 10). Out of 573 building unit total which there are located in Setui, 251 unit (less than 50 percent) having level of high resistance. Interesting fact, if we compare between buildings age map and level of buildings resistances, where buildings with age more than 30 years (old building) generally have level of low resistance. Low resistance means that building which old in age especially more than 30 year is easy to experience damage as impact of occurrence of earthquake.

CONCLUSION

- [1] The available of building information system could be used for identification and fast calculation of victim and physical damage as impact of earthquake especially in high density building in urban area.
- [2] Building with number of floors are one and number of people less than 10 dominating in Setui village reaching around 80 percent and generally experience damage at level G1 and G2.
- [3] More than 35 percent of buildings in Setui have size between 101 and 200 m² and around 88 percents consist of 2 – 5 rooms. Type of building usage predominated by non commercial building/dwelling with more than 90 percents.
- [4] The age of buildings in Setui village are between 3 until 40 years.
- [5] Building with commercial function and located along of Primary Street have age older than 30 years with size of building generally wider than others part and have level of low earthquake resistance (less than 5 in Richter Scale)

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